

Enhancement of OpenAIRE Services

DEC 2018

Advancing Open Scholarship

D10.2 – Enhancement of OpenAIRE Services

Version 1.0 – Final

PUBLIC

This deliverable describes the enhancements of OpenAIRE Services to integrate requested end-user functionalities. The services belong to the aggregation, information space publishing and, added-value services sub-systems.

H2020-EINFRA-2017
Grant Agreement 777541

Document Description

D10.2 – Enhancement of OpenAIRE Services

WP10 - Optimization & Upgrade of OpenAIRE Technical Services	
WP participating organizations: CNR, ICM, CERN, ARC, ARC/GRNET, UNIBI, UBONN	
Contractual Delivery Date: 08/2018	Actual Delivery Date: 01/2019
Nature: Report	Version: 1.0 (Final)
Public Deliverable	

Preparation Slip

	Name	Organisation	Date
From	Antonis Lempesis	ARC	12/2018
	Claudio Atzori	CNR	10/2018
	Paolo Manghi	CNR	10/2018
	Aenne Löhden	UNIBI	10/2018
	Katerina Iatropoulou	ARC	10/2018
	Argiro Kokogiannaki	ARC	10/2018
	Sahar Vahdati	UBONN	11/2018
	Giorgos Alexiou	ARC	11/2018
	Jochen Schirrwagen	UNIBI	10/2018
	Dimitris Pierrakos	ARC	10/2018
	Manolis Terrovitis	ARC	11/2018
George Kakaletis	ARC	11/2018	
Edited by	Katerina Iatropoulou	ARC	12/2018
Reviewed by	Natalia Manola	UOA	12/2018
	Claudio Atzori	CNR	12/2018
Approved by	Natalia Manola	UOA	01/2019
For delivery	Mike Chatzopoulos	UoA	01/2019

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This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Union. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the OpenAIRE-Advance consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

OpenAIRE-Advance is a project funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement No 777541).

Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
BASE	Bielefeld Academic Search Engine
CSV	Comma separated values
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FRBR	Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
JATS	Journal Article Tag Set
LOD	Linked Open Data
MyCoRe	My Content Repository
NOAD	National Open Access Desk
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OJS	Open Journal Systems
OpenDOAR	Directory of Open Access Repositories
OpenMinTeD	Open Mining INfrastructure for TExt and Data
PI	Principal Investigator
PID	Persistent Identifier
re3data	Registry of Research Data Repositories
REST	Representational State Transfer
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
XSLT	Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations

Publishable Summary

This deliverable describes the enhancements of OpenAIRE Services with respect to planned and requested end user functionalities.

In particular, this document elaborates on the following services and related areas:

- How the **Validator Service** will ensure better quality of the metadata coming from repositories, while facing the challenge to support larger number of records and new APIs.
- On the **aggregation** level, it is explained how efforts on metadata analysis and proper transformation mappings of the original metadata will result to better metadata quality for the end users.
- Ways of improving end user interaction with Open AIRE, and in particular how users/researchers can help in the enrichment and validation of data (errors and duplicate identification).
- Enhanced **LOD Services** to interlink and integrate of OpenAIRE data with other datasets (e.g., WikiCite, CORDIS and WikiBase ERC).
- How the **Broker Service** will be extended to offer subscriptions for repositories and to support new functionalities for the Research Community Dashboard.
- Scaling up the **Usage Metrics Services** and extending it with visualization and reporting features.
- Information Space **Interlinking Services** to allow OpenAIRE to serve any requesting data source with enrichment functionalities.
- **Amnesia** improvements to simplify the anonymization procedures, support new algorithms and larger number of datasets that can be anonymized.
- What kinds of enhancements will be applied to the emerging OpenAIRE **DMP service** to ensure coverage of community based templates and requests, and improvements to make the interface more engaging to researchers.

1 | VALIDATION SERVICE

1.1 Current Status

The OpenAIRE Validator Service is a key OpenAIRE service offered to the content providers through the PROVIDE Dashboard and it implements and verifies the compatibility to the OpenAIRE Guidelines. Its main characteristics are:

- Has been in production for several years
- Robust and tested service, able to easily handle the current validation needs of OpenAIRE.
- Able to validate, score and keep a history of past validations
- A rule based service, supporting the configuration of the validation according to Guidelines which conform to some rules
- It provides an easy to use admin interface that allows administrators to express the rules via adding/modifying/deleting them

1.2 Proposed Enhancements

1.2.1 Objectives

Two key objectives drive the developments in the Validation Service:

- ▣ The new Content Acquisition Policy¹ and the inclusion of additional databases (e.g., CrossRef², DataCite) will increase the number of harvested metadata records to rise to ~140 million.
- ▣ Continuous validation, embedded into the harvesting, is required to correct metadata. This will allow for automated progress recording for compatibility of data sources.

While the Validator service serves the current needs of content providers, the increase in both the number of metadata and the frequency of validations makes it necessary to radically improve the service's throughput.

These translate to the following enhancements:

- ▣ **Validator as a service (Continuous validation).** This will require a tighter integration of the existing service implementation with the DNet framework that will allow it to become part of the OpenAIRE workflows. The service will therefore be able to validate contents of the metadata stores and provide a much richer report than what is available now.
- ▣ **Support for new APIs (ResourceSync).** The current implementation of the Validator service harvests repositories via the OAI-PMH interface. While this is a de facto standard, new and more efficient protocols are being proposed and gradually adopted. The Validator Service will be enhanced to support these new protocols, with ResourceSync being first in line.

¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/content-acquisition-policy>

² <http://crossref.org/>

- **Support for much larger number of records.** Even though validator service has been proven to easily handle content from repositories now registered in OpenAIRE, the decision to add validation in the aggregation workflows combined with the increase in the number of metadata (more than 100 million records) lead to a huge increase to the workload of the service. The validator service will be enhanced to support distributed execution to greatly improve its throughput.
- **Improved support for CRIS validation.** The current version of the validation provides rudimentary support for CRIS validation. We plan to evaluate and improve the implementation for CRIS to properly support aggregation of CERIF compliant metadata.
- **Support for new rule classes.** The validator service is a rule based engine that awards a score by evaluating rules against the metadata of the publications. The existing rules belong to a small number of classes (e.g. “metadata element X must appear exactly once” or “the element Y must have a specific format”). With the better support for CRIS validation, new classes of rules are expected to be needed.
- **Support for JSON format.** While the majority of the publication metadata are expressed in XML, JSON format is rapidly being adopted. For this reason, the validator service must be able to validate metadata in JSON.
- **The validator will no longer be used for datasource registration.** With the implementation and deployment of the Content Provider dashboard, datasource administrators have now the option to manage their datasource using the dashboard. The datasource management functionality will be removed from the validator user interfaces.

1.2.2 Technical Specifications

To avoid significant (with potentially lengthy development and testing phases) changes in the current implementation, the plan is to substitute the current execution engine (which is now using a single node and supports multiple threads) with a distributed execution engine, like Hazelcast³ or Apache Ignite⁴. This change will allow the validator service to effectively scale to a cluster, thus providing a much higher throughput.

Validation of metadata in JSON requires the use of appropriate libraries, namely JSON-path and JSON-schema. The existing rule classes that currently support only XML must be enhanced to also support JSON.

To support continuous validation, the validator service will be enhanced to support the DNet subscription/notification mechanism.

Finally, in order to support datasources with different APIs, we will implement two new harvesters: one consuming records from ResourceSync enabled repositories and another one that consumes records from the OpenAIRE metadata stores (the latter will be used for the continuous validation functionality).

³ <https://hazelcast.org/>

⁴ <https://ignite.apache.org/>

1.3 Integration to production

All new functionality will be in addition to the pre-existing one. As such, the integration with the production infrastructure will follow the typical OpenAIRE procedure: after local and integration tests using the test infrastructure, the new service will be deployed in the beta infrastructure. After a period of testing, first internally by the consortium and then by external users, the service will be deployed to the production infrastructure.

1.3.1 Interaction with other services

- **Content Provider Dashboard.** The content provider dashboard is the only user interface currently providing the validator services' functionality. Few changes are expected since most of the changes will improve the performance and not the functionality of the validator service.
- **Manager Service.** The Manager service is responsible for orchestrating and monitoring the execution of the workflows in DNet. By adding the Validator Service as an additional step in the harvesting workflows, we implicitly allow the Manager service to interact, assign jobs and monitor the operation of the Validator Service.

1.3.2 Timeline (releases)

The Validator Service will receive updates and optimizations throughout the duration of the project. However, the main priority is the ability to support continuous validation while being also able to handle the increase in the number of publication metadata. Those functionalities will be included in MS35 (OpenAIRE D-NET services enhancement: information space publishing sub-system). The rest of the planned changes will be gradually implemented until the end of the project.

2 | AGGREGATION SERVICE

The OpenAIRE Aggregation Service is the central backend component to collect metadata about different kinds of entities (datasources, research results, funding information, organizations, author profiles) from authoritative services, repositories, aggregators and publishing platforms. The metadata are cleaned, harmonized and transformed into a representation so that they can be further processed by other OpenAIRE services according to the OpenAIRE data model. In addition to the metadata and in case of literature publications the fulltext is located and downloaded for the purpose of text and data mining if permitted by licenses and / or by consent with the datasource manager.

This section examines how to attain prime metadata quality during the aggregation process and discusses aspects of the Datasource API management user interface.

A central point in this matter is the analysis of the originally collected metadata, as profound comprehension of the native metadata is crucial for defining proper transformation mappings, keeping them up to date, and backtracking propagation of errors in the system. Yet, to more comprehensively glance at metadata quality and tackle options to improve it, at first metadata quality facets are listed. Then, steps of metadata processing and sites of metadata perception are visited, and issues and measures named.

What is metadata quality? Metadata quality may refer to several facets. The following list is not a definition but might rather serve as a stimulus for consideration:

TABLE 1. METADATA QUALITY CHARACTERISTICS

Metadata Quality Characteristics	
Timeliness	Metadata should be up-to-date, i.e. records should reflect the current state incl. recent changes
Completeness	All proper, suitable records of datasources as well as all relevant statements of records are leveraged. To incorporate all relevant, apt datasources might be pondered
Accuracy	The information is veritable, correct, and non-contradictory. Also, it should be clear to which items a record's statements refer (e.g. access rights may refer to the metadata record itself or to the described publication, or PIDs may refer to the described publication or to articles cited by it). Statements should also be sound, i.e. PIDs should be valid
Legibility	The descriptions are easily comprehensible, for example due to language (of e.g. titles), structure (of e.g. thesauri/vocabulary), homogeneity (e.g. order of author names).
Consolidation	Records (and statements) are non-redundant, i.e. without duplicates. Also, records are contextualised, i.e. linked with other records (this refers to e.g. citations/references, versions/variants (see also FRBR))
Wastelessness	There are no test records, no records out of scope, no records of predatory sources, no spam records, etc.
Format-conformance	Compliance with format standards, utilization of vocabularies/thesauri.

Other points, which are also relevant regarding the notion of metadata quality may also apply such as information like provenance or access rights, which are crucial to be included in the metadata.

2.1 Current status

In the following, issues and challenges affecting metadata quality are sketched along the metadata's path into, within, and outwards from OpenAIRE.

The complete workflow from registration of a data provider to aggregation and metadata storage is composed of the following six steps:

STEP 1. DATAPROVIDER REGISTRATION

At the site of datasources, metadata is recorded and exposed for collection. While OpenAIRE has issued Guidelines for Repository Managers (<https://guidelines.openaire.eu>) regarding recommended syntax and semantics to be used in metadata values the resulting quality of the metadata integrated in OpenAIRE may vary greatly and depend on different aspects:

TABLE 2. DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF DATASOURCES AND METADATA INTEGRATED IN OPENAIRE

Different aspects of datasources and metadata integrated in OpenAIRE	
Platforms	Datasources employ diverse (repository) software, like DSpace, EPrints, Fedora, Invenio, MyCoRe, OJS. For some of the platforms, OpenAIRE plugins provide specific support (e.g. to include funding statements in the metadata).
Countries	Datasources are located on all continents
Source types	OpenAIRE integrates metadata from e.g. institutes', journals', aggregators', publishers', communities', or thematic repositories
Publication types	Publication types fall under the categories literature, data, software, and other research output
Languages	Both research output and its metadata comes in numerous languages
Formats	Metadata follows the OpenAIRE guidelines or standards like Dublin Core, DataCite5, JATS, or others
Interfaces	Metadata is exposed via miscellaneous interfaces like OAI-PMH, REST, FTP, dumps, and others
Personnel	The staff registering publications might be unfamiliar with metadata and repositories, or a datasource might embrace diverse self-dependent spheres and personnel (like journals being attended to by journal specific editors and in virtual platform domains within publisher platforms)

These diversities induce typical/common variations (e.g. values of a property provided in different fields; use of not agreed vocabularies), mistakes, or lacks in the metadata. Additionally, many datasources feature unique variations, mistakes, or lacks.

⁵ <https://www.datacite.org>

Usually, datasources are registered to OpenAIRE by their administrators. During this process the datasource metadata are initially validated against OpenAIRE's guidelines (tool: www.openaire.eu/validator). Often, datasource administrators are intellectually given feedback on their metadata's quality and are asked for improvements, which they frequently are happy to satisfy.

Frequently received feedback from datasource administrators indicate some shortcomings, e.g. with regard to funding information:

- Support for including funding attributes is not optimal, as i) the set of funders supported by OpenAIRE is not always obvious, ii) the means (e.g. plugins) chipping in with e.g. project identifiers or funder identifiers are not available for all platforms and/or do not cover all funders.

STEP 2. METADATA INTERFACES SET UP WITHIN OPENAIRE

By registration of a datasource in OpenAIRE, its API protocol and metadata profile is configured. Before starting the aggregation the configuration is manually checked again and workflows for harvesting, continuous validation and transformation are added (tool: DataSource API Management). If needed the datasource manager is contacted to solve issues on user requests, interface details, error hints or change requirements via OpenAIRE's communication channels.

STEP 3. DATASOURCE'S METADATA ANALYSIS

To deal with deviations within the collected (original/native) metadata, each datasource's metadata then is to be analysed individually and intellectually. The metadata records can be viewed, per datasource, in bunches and trawled with regular expressions (grep on md-store). The available functionality poses the following issues:

- When viewing metadata, its datasource, interface, or aggregation level (collected or transformed) are not indicated (workaround: peer at datasource or record identifiers, OpenAIRE specific fields added by transformation, number of records). [Figure 1]
- Searching with regular expressions often breaks at the second page, and then shows either all records (dropping the search) or just a blank page. Thus, only the first 10 search results are viewable.
- Searching in big datasources is very slow.
- Searching in very big datasources (>100K records) fails due to timeout error.
- Comprehensively trawling the metadata of several or all datasources is not feasible.
- Statistics about metadata fields and values cannot be surveyed.
- Supported search expressions (regular and logical expressions) are limited (e.g. searching for records missing some data (negative grep) is not feasible).

MDStore details

GREP: REPLACEMENT: Replace?

Show from: 0 ([prev](#)) out of 6418 ([next](#))

[edit](#) [delete](#)

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<oi:record xmlns="http://namespace.openaire.eu/"
  xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/"
  xmlns:dr="http://www.driver-repository.eu/namespace/dr"
  xmlns:dri="http://www.driver-repository.eu/namespace/dri"
  xmlns:oaf="http://namespace.openaire.eu/oaf"
  xmlns:oai="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/"
  xmlns:prov="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/provenance" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/ http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/OAI-2.0.xsd">
  <oi:header>
    <dri:objIdentifier>od_____2347::0014dcfc1ada765afb9766f332142681</dri:objIdentifier>
    <dri:recordIdentifier>oai:academica-e.unavarra.es:2454/7950</dri:recordIdentifier>
```

FIGURE 1 - VIEWING METADATA WITHOUT INDICATION ON DATASOURCE, INTERFACE, AGGREGATION LEVEL.

STEP 4. PREPARE OPENAIRE FORMAT TRANSFORMATION

After analysing a datasource's metadata, its transformation to the internal OpenAIRE format is prepared. Transformation rules are based on XSLT and rely on DNET vocabularies. Metadata transformation can be tested for single records by help of the transformation inspector.

For metadata gathered from other aggregators or publishers, the original datasource or initial provenance is to be determined.

STEP 5. OPENAIRE AGGREGATION

Once integrated, a datasource metadata can be regularly aggregated in OpenAIRE. This step includes harvesting and transformation that are automatically and periodically launched (Cron jobs).

Harvesting and transformation can be conducted in incremental or refresh mode. While some datasources explicitly announce deleted records, others just stop exposing them.

A workflow history on aggregation jobs is also provided, however the workflow history does not accommodate conveniently checking for broken datasource aggregation [Figure 2] while information on background/error for broken datasource aggregation is meagre.

wf_20180807_04163...	collection	aggregator	Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Açık Erişim Sistemi	FAILURE	2018-08-07 ..
wf_20180804_04162...	collection	aggregator	Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Açık Erişim Sistemi	FAILURE	2018-08-04 ..
wf_20180805_04362...	collection	aggregator	Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Açık Erişim Sistemi	FAILURE	2018-08-05 ..
wf_20180807_04361...	collection	aggregator	Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Açık Erişim Sistemi	FAILURE	2018-08-07 ..
wf_20180803_04162...	collection	aggregator	Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Açık Erişim Sistemi	FAILURE	2018-08-03 ..
wf_20180810_04162...	collection	aggregator	Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Açık Erişim Sistemi	FAILURE	2018-08-10 ..
wf_20180806_04162...	collection	aggregator	Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Açık Erişim Sistemi	FAILURE	2018-08-06 ..

FIGURE 2 - WORKFLOW HISTORY DOES NOT ALLOW SORTING BOTH BY DATASOURCE AND BY TIME

STEP 6. OPENAIRE METADATA POST PROCESSING

Finally, OpenAIRE post-processes and enriches, indexes, and exposes the metadata:

- Duplicate records of entities (publications, organisations) are merged; user claims are evaluated; fulltexts are mined for further information.
- The metadata is indexed and exposed on OpenAIRE's portal as well as via its APIs.

2.2 Proposed Enhancements

2.2.1 Objectives

The proposed enhancements aim for advancing metadata quality are:

- Expose extensive, rich, sound metadata.
- Improve exposition, lucidity, legibility of metadata.
- Leverage metadata richness, i.e. utilise all worthwhile information instead of wasting it by disregard.
- Integrate many datasources, even if not fully conforming to OpenAIRE's guidelines.
- Make metadata aggregation more efficient, thus fostering metadata curation.
- Improve exposition and retrieval of all types of publications (no matter if literature, research data, software, or other) and datasources (incl. indirectly harvested ones).
- Support datasource administrators, project coordinators, or authors to improve their metadata.
- Minimize downtime of datasources' aggregation workflows, thus fostering metadata timeliness, completeness, wastelessness.
- Provide benefit to different types of users and usages (scientists, project coordinators, funders).
- Offer transparency concerning metadata aggregation.

TABLE 3. AGGREGATION ENHANCEMENT TOPICS

Aggregation Enhancement Topics	
Metadata and fulltext provision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Publish a maintained list of supported funders, incl. future funders ones – Provide built-in or plugin support of dataprovider software to comply with the latest OpenAIRE Guidelines – Clarify permission of fulltext harvesting by OpenAIRE including fulltext reuse by third parties (like OpenMinTeD) to increase the number of datasources from which fulltexts may be loaded.
Usability and navigation of the Datasource API Management User Interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – User registrations become more clear: We need to display users' requests to update their datasource integration more verbosely, i.e. show which data exactly they asked to change. – Improve the editing environment for transformation scripts – Provide fields to store comments, links to tickets
Metadata analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Support indexing of collected metadata to improve metadata analysis and evaluation of field-value statistics
Metadata transformation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Ease testing metadata transformation by improved integration of the transformation inspector and linking with the transformation editor – Improve the procedure to identify original datasources when collected from aggregators (for repositories) or publisher platforms (hosting journals) and integrate this kind of information in the OpenAIRE database for datasources; e.g. metadata of the same research result might be collected from different dataproviders – Enable periodic refresh for aggregation jobs configured in incremental mode to keep metadata in sync. – Extend log history of jobs with all aggregation parameters used
DNET vocabularies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Revise the current vocabulary of resource types

2.2.2 Technical specs

The proposed enhancements concerning the Datasource Management User Interface can be implemented in revised versions of DNET software libraries.

The metadata transformation engine needs to be updated to comply with the latest version of the SAXON XSLT library to support XSLT 3.0, XPath 2.0 and 3.1, and XQuery 3.1 and thus improve features and performance of transformation rules. Furthermore operating on JSON formatted metadata needs to be added.

The output format of transformation services should be in a representation that can be exploited directly in HBase to avoid additional conversion steps and to improve performance.

The introduction of an indexing step after metadata collection requires an additional Solr index or the use of Elasticsearch or Kibana technology.

2.3 Integration in production

To extend the available functionality of basic metadata analysis with the option of detailed, overall metadata analysis, new tools should be introduced beside the existing environment. Although the requirements as listed above should be further detailed, an informal survey and trial had already shown Kibana to be a beneficial choice. Kibana is to be accompanied by Elasticsearch⁶. Due diligence should be spent on configuration of Elasticsearch and Kibana, e.g. in order to cope with quite heterogeneous formats. Detailed metadata analysis is at least needed on production, yet monitoring on production and beta would be ideal.

In general, all new functionalities will extend the pre-existing one. To this aim, the integration with the production infrastructure will follow the established OpenAIRE procedure: after local and integration tests using the development infrastructure, the new functionalities will be deployed in the beta infrastructure. After a period of testing, first internally by the consortium and then by external users, the service will be deployed to the production infrastructure.

2.3.1 Interaction with other services

The aggregator service depends on the registration and validation service with regard to aggregation configurations as well as with evaluating metadata quality against the OpenAIRE Guidelines. It orchestrates the flow of input data collected from the data providers as well as further data processing steps, from the metadata transformation to the execution of the deduplication and inference workflows. Relevant information produced by the different processes orchestrations is made available to the front-end services from various backing systems via dedicated REST API. Among this relevant information we can mention:

- The metadata collection/transformation time
- The number of collected/transformed metadata records

⁶ <https://www.elastic.co>

2.3.2 Timeline (releases)

Although some of the proposed enhancements were already addressed in the first 12 months (MS33 - OpenAIRE DNet software for optimization) and are already delivered in production, we plan the introduction of the latest SAXON XSLT library, support for JSON formatted metadata and revision of the transformation output format to be addressed in the next 12 months, together with the detailed evaluation of the requirements for the introduction of Kibana and Elasticsearch, that will be delivered in production by M36, following the usual procedure of deployment in BETA for testing and release in production after end-user validation.

3 | END-USER CORRECTIVE FEEDBACK

Currently, metadata quality is primarily taken care of by parties related to the depositing/publishing datasources (repository managers, journal editors, authors, project coordinators) and OpenAIRE data curators. Due to the high volume and heterogeneity of metadata, many metadata flaws persist and propagate throughout the harvesting/transformation/publishing processes and remain unattended. End-users (researchers, project coordinators, research administrators and funders) are a valuable source of information giving feedback and correcting or complementing metadata as discovered and viewed in the OpenAIRE portal (Explore⁷).

3.1 Current status

End users interact with OpenAIRE to report issues on the metadata quality:

- **Data providers & PIs**, mainly interested in raising the visibility of their data repository or institution respectively.
- **Funders & research administrators**, interested in publicizing and disseminating the results of their project and, thereby achieving the increasing of the projects’ impact.
- **Researchers**, interested in opening their research to a wider audience, increase their citations number.

Some interactions help improve metadata quality, some reveal users' expectations on OpenAIRE's metadata quality. The first two groups of users usually “intervene” for information related to their repository, institution, project and research community and for relevant content. The following table shows the most common requests.

TABLE 4. USERS’ REQUESTS ON METADATA

Users’ Requests on Metadata	
Information Related	Change some of their organizational data (like name, interface URL, etc.)
	Remove duplicate entries for their organization
	Relate them with other organizations (e.g. a data repository or a project with an institution)
Content Related	Add missing research records of research results
	Remove the record of a research result
	Remove duplicate entries records of research results
	Add missing information for a research result (e.g. missing funding information)

⁷ <https://explore.openaire.eu>

The channels of this communications are the **helpdesk**, OpenAIRE members' individual **contact forms**, **emails**, **social media** (twitter, LinkedIn) and OpenAIRE **GitHub**.

In addition, researchers and PIs are also able to “**claim**” publications/datasets/software and link them together or to their grants, therefore indirectly enriching the OpenAIRE graph. There are three possible kinds of links, between:

- research products and funding, community, and access rights information.
- records from external resources (e.g. CrossRef⁸, DataCite⁹, ORCID¹⁰) and information already available in OpenAIRE (e.g. project and communities), in which case external records become part of the OpenAIRE content.
- research products (e.g. publication with research data and software).

3.2 Proposed Enhancements

3.2.1 Objectives

As end-users (researchers, PIs, funders, research administrators) are a valuable source of authoritative information for the improvement of metadata quality, we need to foster and encourage the provision of such information. The ways to achieve that are:

- through functionalities that offer new ways of metadata enrichment.
- through the gradual improvement of metadata quality itself.

These will serve the following main objectives of end-user corrective feedback:

- Provide functionalities that support seamless end-users feedback.
- Build a sound and solid interaction with end-users.
- Improve OpenAIRE’s metadata quality.

These objectives are intertwined; functionalities that allow users to effortlessly improve metadata quality, encourage them to give more feedback that serves the enhancement of OpenAIRE content. In turn, improved content kindles the users’ interest in providing more of their valuable information.

3.2.2 Technical specs

CLAIMING SERVICE ENHANCEMENT

Users “claim” functionality is provided mainly through the OpenAIRE EXPLORE Dashboard supported by the underlying Claim Service. It consists of two main parts: the discovery and identification of the entities to be interlinked and the process of validating and storing the links.

The discovery and identification of interlinked entities are done via forms in the EXPLORE Dashboard (Angular) which that allow users to search by keywords and PIDs. The Angular portal

⁸ <https://www.crossref.org>

⁹ <https://www.datacite.org>

¹⁰ <https://orcid.org>

then makes GET requests to REST APIs internal or external to OpenAIRE. For the discovery of grant information and OpenAIRE entities, the portal interacts with the OpenAIRE Search REST APIs¹¹. For external entities, it interacts with REST APIs that pass the DOIs (CrossRef¹², DataCite¹³), keywords (CrossRef, DataCite and ORCID¹⁴) and ORCID (ORCID) that were typed by users. Once the JSON response that contains the entities' records is received, it is parsed, and a summary of the most representative metadata is presented to the users. After they have selected the entities they wish to link, and when they click the save button, the portal makes a POST request to the Claim Service REST API, containing the information required (basic metadata, PIDs, OpenAIRE Ids and the metadata record) and saves the new links in the Claims DB (Mongo DB¹⁵) and the OpenAIRE graph.

FIGURE 3 - CLAIM FUNCTIONALITY

As the types of research products are enriched, new ways of identifying research products will be introduced; one way is to allow the use of other types of PIDs beyond DOIs, e.g. URNs or Handles. Also, new external resources will be added; for example, Zotero¹⁶, a free, open-source research tool that helps collect, organize, and analyse bibliographic data and related research materials.

The main requirement for external resources to be integrated in OpenAIRE claim functionality is to provide REST APIs that allow keyword and/or PID searches in their contents. The basic addition in the previously described process is the enhancement of the parsing of JSON responses, according to the schema that each external resource follows. The Claims DB poses no limitation in the storage of new external entities as their metadata record is saved as is.

CURATION & NOTIFICATIONS

Currently the links inserted via the end-user feedback process are automatically accepted as valid, which may not always be the case as not all users have the same authoritativeness. In the upcoming versions of the EXPLORE Dashboard, special users such as project and research

¹¹ <https://api.openaire.eu>

¹² <https://www.crossref.org/services/metadata-delivery/rest-api/>

¹³ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/api>

¹⁴ <https://orcid.org/organizations/integrators/API>

¹⁵ <https://www.mongodb.com>

¹⁶ https://www.zotero.org/support/dev/web_api/v3/write_requests#rest_approach

community managers, will be able to overview all submitted links and remove the ones that may not be valid. This is a crucial enhancement, as it gives more power to research communities and alleviates the burden from the OpenAIRE technical team, which has been since a few year acting as moderators (handling requests which arrive via e-mail or helpdesk tickets).

To achieve that, a Java thread will run offline daily, to check in the Claims DB what new links were submitted. Project and community managers will receive e-mail notifications that will

- inform them about new links concerning their project or community.
- provide links to special curation pages.

These curation pages will only be accessible to privileged (research & project managers) users. They will offer an overview of the submitted links, and a basic curation functionality; if the submitted links are not valid, the special users will be able to remove them. For this to happen, the Claim Service REST API will be extended to provide additional GET and POST methods that allow the retrieval of links and their deletion.

An important feature is that the curation pages will be implemented as configurable Angular components. This will make them reusable to other Angular Dashboards, namely for the Funder/Project and Institutional ones. In that way the curation functionality can be propagated within OpenAIRE to all portals that can find it useful to their users.

BROKER SERVICE

Data providers will be notified for the feedback received through the OpenAIRE Broker Services. This means that links validated by projects and research community managers will generate enrichment events for the Broker Service that will in turn notify repository managers about the availability of new links. More information about the extensions planned for the broker service and its implementation are described in 5| The OpenAIRE Broker Services.

FIGURE 4 - LINK MANAGEMENT PAGE FOR RESEARCH COMMUNITY MANAGER

3.3 Integration in production

3.3.1 Interaction with other services

For the claiming functionality, as mentioned above, possibilities of adding new external sources and new ways to identify research products will be examined. For the new identified sources the Claiming Service and the portal will be enhanced to interact with them, through REST or Java APIs. As it is already done with the existing sources, the metadata of the identified research products will be fetched and modified into the OpenAIRE data schema to be stored and inserted into the OpenAIRE Information Space.

As mentioned in the previous paragraph interaction with the Broker Services will be needed to achieve the notification of data providers for the user feedback received.

3.3.2 Timeline (releases)

For the claiming functionality, possibilities of adding new external sources and new ways to identify research products will be examined and when possible adopted. This will happen throughout all the project lifecycle.

The curation of links by research community managers is already available in BETA. Besides, e-mail notifications are sent to research community managers regularly after the addition of a new link by a user. Those functionalities are currently under testing and usability assessment. Once fully tested and evaluated, it will be revised if necessary and made available in production before M24. For the Funder/Project and Institutional Dashboards the same curation functionality will be available by M24. By M24 there will also be available the interaction with the Broker Services.

4 | LOD ENRICHMENTS

4.1 Current status

The Internet detonated with a substantial and a wide assortment of information over the last few years. So researchers tried to find different strategies to deal with such huge data. One such strategy is interlinking. In interlinking we find similar data in different datasets. In this research effort, we have built a novel mechanism based on Apache Spark for performing the interlinking task over big RDF graphs. The proposed mechanism is the result of our research in the entity resolution domain along with the big data domain. It implements methods and algorithms, such as blocking and meta-blocking over distributed systems, for fast and scalable entity resolution over big data. More specifically the mechanism can be described in 9 distinct steps.

1. **Data Reading:** The input of source and target datasets from HDFS)

2. **Data Filtering:** In this step, we filter out the entities that we want to interlink for performance reasons (e.g., Publications)
3. **Data Union:** In this step, we perform a union of the two datasets to create a single RDD (spark data structure) that we will persist in memory for performance reasons. (Note that we annotate source and target entities for future use)
4. **Token Blocking:** Using that mappings for each dataset we create tokens in the form of (token, resource_id) to create the blocks in a later step
5. **Purging:** since token blocking creates many redundant pairs and to increase our performance we perform a purging step for decreasing the total number of the aforementioned pairs, which actually decreases the total number of pairwise comparisons

in the end, thus increasing the performance of the system. The purging is based on the mathematical formula below, where b_i is the size of the block i .

$$CC = \frac{\sum b_i |b_i|}{\sum b_i |b_i| + (|b_i| - 1)/2}$$

6. **Inverted Index:** In this step we create an inverted index in the form of (resource_id [token, resource_id]) in order to be utilized in the creation of the final blocks.
7. **Blocks Creation:** Utilizing the inverted index the information from the unioned RDD we create the final blocks in the form of (token [resource_id, resource_metadata])
8. **Interlinking:** In this step we perform pairwise comparisons but only within each block, thus reducing the overall size of comparisons, in order to determine the sameAs relations between the resources of the two distinct datasets, i.e., OpenAIRE dataset (source) - external dataset (target). In this steps for the final comparisons we utilize the LIMES framework. More specifically, the mechanism iterates over all blocks collection and for each block it creates a source and a target dataset. These datasets are used as input in a LIMES instance along with the LIMES configuration file, which holds the mappings, to perform the final pairwise comparisons.
9. **Production of Linkset:** The output of each LIMES instance that runs for every block in the block collection is coalesced from the distributed nodes in the cluster and stored directly on the HDFS in the form of <source_uri> <owl:sameAs> <target_uri>.

The output of the described mechanism is bulk loaded with an established workflow directly in our triple store (Openlink Virtuoso), which makes it publicly available and ready for consumption.

Note: Utilizing the aforementioned workflow of the Spark application, we have managed so far to interlink OpenAIRE with 3 big external datasets, namely DBLP, OpenCitations and Wikidata, with Wikidata being the biggest of all (data dump 1.3 TB). The output of this effort produced several millions of links between the OpenAIRE LOD graph and these graphs, which could be exploited in later steps to produce new and valuable knowledge.

4.2 Proposed Enhancements

4.2.1 Objectives

The task of interlinking the RDFized data of OpenAIRE with other relevant datasets on the LOD cloud is aimed to expand the information space. It requires a chain of continuous evolution steps on the side of OpenAIRE data schema to be compatible with terms of the other standard vocabularies. The LOD team pursued a broad approach w.r.t. interlinking, addressing all the following types of datasets forming interlinking targets:

- data that has not (yet) been collected by OpenAIRE's existing mechanisms, e.g., certain types of persistent identifiers of publications or people (e.g., ORCID),

- data that is expensive to collect and/or not included in the current OpenAIRE data model, e.g., data about scientific events, and
- data that is related to open research but out of the scope of the OpenAIRE infrastructure itself and therefore not targeted to be ever collected, e.g., biographies of persons, or geodata about the locations of organizations.

Currently the interlinking activities of OA LOD team is focused with the purpose of enriching the OA information space. 30+ candidate target datasets have been analyzed, reported in OpenAIRE2020 and gradually increasing. 2 of them, DBLP (600K sameAs links) and OpenCitations (1.8 M sameAs links) were fully interlinked in OpenAIRE2020; in the current phase of OA project, the interlinking with Wikidata is done (7.1 M sameAs links), and it is planned to further interlink with other target datasets such as WikiCite, CORDIS and WikiBase ERC were specified and planned. One use case for interlinking for example with WikiBase ERC is that they have grant information of the ERC projects, which is useful information for OA to expand the information space and provide high quality statistics and interesting insights. This can impact the overall research and funding in the level of European Union. The integration of OA with other datasets is planned to be done with the aim of expanding the overall information space and schema of OA. Some example use cases of integration with Wikibase would be to provide statistics about the relatedness of organizations with funding of projects on the level of EU and the evaluations on the impact of such fundings on the development of topics and research results.

4.2.2 Technical specs

The LOD enrichments are designed to extend the already established mechanism that LOD utilizes to produce the information in RDF descriptions. The mechanism was designed and evaluated several times (mainly in OpenAIRE2020 with final scalability adoptions in OpenAIRE-Advance, as explained in 4.1). The current RDFization is maintainable and scalable with a high performance. The main focus of the OA LOD services in this phase is the interlinking and integration of OA information space with other datasets. Technically, the first step to identify potential datasets to be interlinked with and apply a schema adoption approach between OA LOD and the target datasets. Then providing the datasets in N-Triples format and the mappings as an input for the interlinking mechanism (explained in 4.1). Further improvements and the technical challenges for the LOD team depends on FAIRness of target datasets.

4.3 Integration in production

Integration in production will take place following the usual procedure of deployment in BETA for testing and release in production after end-user validation.

4.3.1 Interaction with other services

The main internal interaction of the OA LOD services with other services is the data transformation from HBase to an RDF representation and with the orchestration service, which coordinates and monitors the RDFization workflow.

4.3.2 Timeline (releases)

The timeline for the upcoming activities in the agenda of the OA LOD team are:

Regular RDFization (the timing is aligned with the updates on the OA information space): Due to the dynamic nature of the OpenAIRE Information Space, its transformation to an RDF representation and its publication as Linked Open Data (LOD) will require regular updates. The vocabulary requires regular evolution to keep up with the evolution of the OpenAIRE Information Space, e.g., most recently, the addition of software as a type of result, which required the introduction of new classes and properties in the vocabulary.

Interlinking (aligned with the RDFization and per updates on the target datasets): On the side of the target dataset, pre-processing activities are crucial and ongoing. One of the challenges for the LOD services is to have an automated interlinking process. In addition, changes of the location and format of the target data as well as their schema need to be checked regularly.

Produce KPIs (end of February 2019): There are certain KPIs that are under preparation namely Statistics about the OA LOD such as comparison of these numbers from last production to the recent production, statistics about the LOD services such as Endpoint visits/usage and the Zenodo downloads, statistics about the LOD in comparison to other datasets in terms of the number of triples in the target datasets e.g., OpenCitations and comparison of entities and sameAs links with OA LOD. Further KPI ideas from LOD services will depend on the status how we connect to LOD cloud with other datasets.

Constantly identify resources and interlink (monthly update is planned to be distributed within the OA technical team): Based on the best practices and the experience of the OA LOD team in the context of the OA project and other activities, this activity can be divided in several time intervals divided into three: period of 1 month, 3 months and 6 months. The interlinking activities are mainly depending on the status of the target dataset. 1 month interlinking efforts are estimated for the target datasets identified to have a high-level relevance for OA with a ready to use RDF dump or accessible SPARQL endpoints. The 3 months interlinking efforts are for those datasets that require further pre-processing of the data. And finally, the 6 months interlinking efforts are for the datasets that require interactions with the data providers, support in providing the maintainable RDF representation of the target dataset and further challenges.

Integration (end of April 2019): One of the ultimate goals of the LOD team is to enrich the information space of OA with the use of external datasets to produce new properties and data. For example, an idea that is under development is to create a citation graph internally within the OA result entities, which does not exist at the moment.

5 | THE OPENAIRE BROKER SERVICES

5.1 Current status

Via the OpenAIRE dashboard for content providers, repository managers can benefit from the notifications delivered by the OpenAIRE Literature Broker Service. The service allows event providers to send to repositories three kinds of events: additions, enrichments, and alerts:

- **Additions** are events regarding the addition of records to a repository: this means that the event provider must be aware of the records available to a repository and realize that a given record is not part of the collection, but should very likely be (e.g. one of the authors is affiliated with the institution operating the repository).
- **Enrichments** are events regarding enhancements of the records in a repository collection: this means the event provider has somehow enriched the original records of the repository.
- **Alerts** are events regarding the identification of mistakes in a repository record, ranging from invalid XMLs, to wrong metadata information: this means the event provider has processed the original records of the repository and realized a mistake was present.

Event providers, properly registered to the broker, can generate events as triples

`<event provider, event message, target repository>`

and send them via APIs to the broker using the OpenAIRE repository identification system (based on OpenDOAR). Content providers can subscribe to given topics relative to enrichments, additions, or alerts and receive the relative notifications. They can also configure selection criteria (restricting notification to matching events based on given authors, title, subject criteria), notification time intervals, and notification means (e.g. via mail or via APIs, for the moment only the former has been implemented).

OpenAIRE has built an event provider service based on the OpenAIRE graph. The ISG is a valuable source for repository managers to improve their repository collections and content, as it may feature information that is not otherwise available to them. Such information is derived largely by the results of two processes: deduplication and inference.

- The deduplication process might merge two records collected from repositories A and B, the service therefore may derive that the record from A can be improved with content from the other record from B and generate a relative event for A.
- The inference process might enrich publication metadata records from repository A by extracting project references from the acknowledgement section of the publication's full-text. The event provider service can therefore generate an enrichment event for the repository A.

FIGURE 5 - THE OPENAIRE BROKER SERVICE

SCALABILITY CHALLENGES

Events are the core of the Broker Service, since they need to be often updated and searched for matching with subscriptions, and may reach very large numbers. A preliminary analysis conducted in 2016 highlighted that, solely for enrichment events and institutional repositories the number of potential “enrichment” notifications, was 28M¹⁷.

In order to make the Broker Events searchable and taking into account the growing number of research artefacts populating the OpenAIRE information space graph, the Broker Service must be built on top of a scalable back-end, efficient on dropping and feeding entries and also capable of supporting efficient queries. The current implementation finds in Elasticsearch¹⁸ full-text index a good fitting candidate among the Open Source search engines due to its capability of scaling up horizontally and the expressivity of its data model and query language.

5.2 Proposed Enhancements

5.2.1 Objectives

As specified in the DoA, the broker will be extended to include new types of topics, hence to provide different forms of subscriptions. At submission time, the DoA was focused on the inclusion of topics regarding the embargo expiration dates and community related topics, such as information about relationships between products and research communities (new entities in OpenAIRE). After almost a year of experience, and the work on the catch-all broker service progressing in OpenAIRE-Connect, we have in mind the more ambitious plan to extend the Broker to:

- Include as consumers of events other kinds of sources, such as data repositories and software repositories;
- Include events regarding enrichments of records with links to projects and other products, such as “publications linked to software”; such events will be generated by extending the OpenAIRE ISG event provider service already operating in OpenAIRE for the current broker deployment;

¹⁷ 10.1007/978-3-319-56300-8_9

¹⁸ www.elastic.co

- Include events regarding alerts, as planned in the original classification of topics; such events should be generated by an event provide service capable of consuming the results of the following OpenAIRE services: transformation service (faulty records from repositories), the validator service (invalid records from the validation), and the end-user feedback service (errors identified by OpenAIRE users that regard information as collected from data sources);
- Include the events regarding embargo expiring date: to be derived thanks to a specific event provider service, matching the embargo dates validity for all publication records;
- Consider other kinds of consumers, such as third-party services willing to consume events within the broker.

We are instead reconsidering the possibility of including topics regarding communities as it is not yet clear if the target repositories would welcome this kind of information, being the communities an OpenAIRE concept, not yet standard across scholarly communication.

5.2.2 Technical specs

The Broker Service has been designed to conform to WS Topics standards, hence to be extendible with any kind of custom subscription. This means that technically, to add a new topic to the broker, we only need to integrate a new “label tree” and integrate a new event provider service capable of generating such events. The services will be developed by CNR with the support of the partners responsible for the event acquisition services, i.e. UNIBI for transformation services and ARC for the validator services.

5.3 Integration in production

Integration in production will take place following the usual procedure of deployment in BETA for testing and release in production after end-user validation.

5.3.1 Interaction with other services

As explained above, the generation of new events requires the definition of event generator services, acquiring information to generate event to be delivered to target repositories. Specifically, the event generators will have to interact with Transformation Services, Validator Services, and End-user feedback services (the internal DB used to “corrective” feedbacks).

5.3.2 Timeline (releases)

The plan is to release the Broker with the new topics by M24, although we expect several new topics will be published before the deadline.

6 | THE OPENAIRE USAGE METRICS SERVICES

The OpenAIRE Usage Statistics Service gathers usage data and consolidated usage statistics reports respectively, from its distributed network of data providers (repositories, e-journals, CRIS) by utilizing open standards and protocols and exploiting reliable, consolidated and comparable usage metrics like counts of item downloads and metadata views conformant to COUNTER¹⁹ Code of Practice (COUNTER CoP).

6.1 Current status

The OpenAIRE Usage Metrics Service operates as a basis for:

- reliable, comparable standards-based statistics (COUNTER-conformant, bot filtering)
- reporting to stakeholders (e.g. as a repository dashboard feature and via the OpenAIRE portal (both currently in their beta versions))
- accumulated usage statistics of repository items which are hosted in multiple data providers (de-duplication)
- provision of usage statistics as an open metric via a standardized API (SUSHI-Lite) for 3rd party re-use.

Two approaches are exploited for the collection of usage data, named Tier 1 and Tier 2, both depicted in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6. THE TWO APPROACHES FOR USAGE STATISTICS AGGREGATION

Tier 1, the default approach, exploits a Push workflow provided by Matomo platform and allows server side tracking of events. Open Access repositories embed tracking code in the form of DSpace patches or EPrints plugins, that exploit Matomo's HTTP API. Usage Activity is tracked and

¹⁹ Counting Online Usage of NeTworked Electronic Resources

logged at Matomo platform in real time. Information is transferred offline, using Matomo's API, to OpenAIRE's DBs for further processing using the COUNTER Code of Practice and statistical analysis. Statistics are subsequently deployed via OpenAIRE's Portal, OpenAIRE's Repository Dashboard or Sushi-Lite API endpoint.

Tier 2, also depicted in Figure 6, follows a Pull workflow, whereas data providers or usage statistics aggregation services (e.g. IRUS-UK) offer a bulk download method for the usage data. In particular, Tier 2 approach supports the gathering of consolidated statistics reports using other protocols such as SUSHI-Lite. These statistics are also stored to OpenAIRE's DB for statistical analysis and are deployed via OpenAIRE's Portal, OpenAIRE's Repository Dashboard, or Sushi-Lite API.

6.2 Proposed Enhancements

6.2.1 Objectives

COUNTER R5

The current version of COUNTER CoP, i.e release 4 will become obsolete, after the final publication of release 5. To stay compliant with COUNTER CoP, OpenAIRE Usage Metrics service should implement the directives of the new release.

COUNTER R5 FOR RESEARCH DATA

OpenAIRE Usage Statistics Service does not implement the Counter CoP R5 for Research Data. The service should be enhanced to comply with this release, since research data will be tracked or aggregated from data providers.

IMPROVE BROWSE AND FILTER OPTIONS FOR USAGE STATISTICS

Static reports are not considered sufficient for exploiting the results of a dynamic service like the OpenAIRE metrics service. Thus, improvements in browsing and filtering options of the service UI, will provide better insights of the usage activity. This will lead to an increase of the number of users that will be engaged with the service.

INTEGRATION OF SUSHI-LITE ENDPOINT AGGREGATION IN THE DATASOURCE MANAGEMENT AND AS A CONFIGURATION / REGISTRATION OPTION IN THE CONTENT PROVIDER DASHBOARD

Lack of support of a management UI for Tier 2 approach is considered a drawback for OpenAIRE's Metric Service. Implementation of registration and configuration of endpoints of data providers in OpenAIRE repository dashboard would alleviate this issue and increase the volume and the quantity of usage data and thus enhance the service itself.

IMPLEMENTATION TOWARDS A USAGE STATISTICS HUB THAT SUPPORTS THE MUTUAL EXCHANGE OF COUNTER COMPLIANT USAGE STATISTICS REPORTS

This enhancement would allow repository managers and hosting institutions to use the hub as a tool to evaluate the success of their publication infrastructures. Authors and readers can exploit the popularity of an individual item among others. Moreover, funding authorities can be informed in research evaluation processes, in addition to other traditional (e.g. citation counts) and alternative metrics (e.g. blogs, social activity, etc.).

In the next paragraphs the proposed enhancements are presented.

UPGRADE TO COUNTER COP R5

COUNTER (Counting Online Usage of NeTworked Electronic Resources) was formally established in March 2002 to facilitate the recording and exchange of usage statistics. The COUNTER Code of Practice provides guidance:

1. on data elements to be measured,
2. definitions of these data elements,
3. output report content and format,
4. data processing and auditing.

OpenAIRE usage statistics and reports are COUNTER-compliant and conform to the Code of Practice Release 4. However, the current release suffers from several shortcomings. It is complex, and shows inconsistencies in reports, the metric types and the supported formats. Most importantly though, is that there are new needs, such as new reporting schemes, to be addressed.

The above are handled by the new release 5 of COUNTER CoP, which seeks a balance between addressing changing needs and reducing the complexity of the Code of Practice to ensure that all publishers and content providers are able to achieve compliance.

COUNTER Cop Release 5 offers consistency in report layout, between formats and in vocabulary. The CoP has been simplified with fewer standard reports and fewer metric types that can be combined with additional item and usage attributes to meet the most common reporting needs. It also adds flexibility through filters and reporting options that address specialized reporting needs avoiding one-off “optional” COUNTER reports. It clearly defines metric types and qualifying actions, processing rules, and formatting expectations.

In terms of SUSHI, Release 5 supports the next release of SUSHI which provides a RESTful interface and JSON-formatted reports. It also allows retrieval of full reports, or snippets of usage and usage display to be embedded in other applications.

IMPLEMENT COUNTER COP FOR RESEARCH DATA

The purpose of the Code of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics is to facilitate the recording, exchange, and interpretation of online usage data by establishing open standards and protocols for the provision of content-provider-generated usage statistics that are consistent, comparable, and credible. This Code of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics is aligned with the COUNTER Code of Practice Release 5 and covers the following areas:

- data elements to be measured,
- definitions of these data elements,
- content and format of usage reports,
- requirements for data processing,
- guidelines to avoid duplicate counting.

The following key definitions are used by the Code of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics:

TABLE 5. KEY DEFINITIONS USED BY THE CODE OF PRACTICE FOR RESEARCH DATA USAGE METRICS

Definitions	
Dataset	An aggregation of data, published or curated by a single agent, and available for access or download in one or more formats, with accompanying metadata. A dataset is a subtype of a COUNTER content item. Synonymous term: data package
Component	Part of the data available for a dataset that can be accessed or downloaded individually. Aligns with a COUNTER component. Synonymous terms: data file, data granule
Collection	A curated aggregation of datasets. Related terms: catalog, repository
Version	Multiple versions of a dataset are defined as significant changes to the content and/or metadata, associated with changes in one or more components, and that would result in changes to fixity attributes of the components.

Code of Practice for Research Data follows the COUNTER Code of Practice Release 5 recommendations as much as possible (where relevant) and deviates from them only when necessary. There are different use cases and practices between research data and most scholarly resources. For example, research data does not need to be reported at the institutional level, but geographic aggregation may be important. Another significant difference is the need for aggregation of usage across components for all versions of a dataset. It is common practice for research data to be versioned, and it is recommended reporting the usage data for each specific version and the combined usage for all versions.

IMPROVE BROWSE AND FILTER OPTIONS FOR USAGE STATISTICS

OpenAIRE’s dashboard for Repository Managers, supports only static reports, in the form of graphs, for usage statistics. Further enhancements are required to provide users with better insights of the tracked items. New browsing and filtering options will be introduced that will allow the delivery of information in a more efficient manner. For example, HTML tables, as well as filtering options like reporting periods, sorting functionalities (e.g. total views in ascending order) and selection of the output format (e.g. JSON, HTML, CSV) will be added.

INTEGRATION OF SUSHI-LITE ENDPOINT AGGREGATION IN THE DATASOURCE MANAGEMENT AND AS A CONFIGURATION / REGISTRATION OPTION IN THE CONTENT PROVIDER DASHBOARD

Current version of OpenAIRE’s dashboard for repository managers limits the registration and configuration to the Tier 1 approach. Tier 2 approach will be supported which enables providers of aggregated usage statistics to register and configure their endpoints to enable OpenAIRE retrieve information.

IMPLEMENTATION TOWARDS A USAGE STATISTICS HUB THAT SUPPORTS THE MUTUAL EXCHANGE OF COUNTER COMPLIANT USAGE STATISTICS REPORTS

OpenAIRE services offer links between publications and datasets. Following this rationale, we consider that linking their usage statistics might make them more valuable and most importantly provide them with better semantics.

Towards this challenge, we propose to enhance the Usage Statistics metrics service via the formation of a network of usage statistics hubs in the frame of the OpenAIRE-Advance project

(<https://www.openaire.eu/advance>). OpenAIRE will do this in collaboration with other usage statistics service providers worldwide, among them IRUS-UK, IRUS-US, IRUS-ANZ, LA-Referencia and MakeDataCount. Such a network of Usage Statistics nodes will not only collect but also enable the distribution and access of the statistical information.

6.2.2 Technical specs

COUNTER R5

- Updates on the post-processing software to comply with the new release of the CoP.
- Updates on the SUSHI-Lite endpoint to support the new reporting schemes.

COUNTER R5 FOR RESEARCH DATA

- Updates on the post-processing software to comply with the CoP for research data.
- Updates on the SUSHI-Lite endpoint to support the reporting schemes of CoP for research data.

IMPROVE BROWSE AND FILTER OPTIONS FOR USAGE STATISTICS

Updates of the OpenAIRE's portal UI and the UI's of the Repository Dashboard are required.

INTEGRATION OF SUSHI-LITE ENDPOINT AGGREGATION IN THE DATASOURCE MANAGEMENT AND AS A CONFIGURATION / REGISTRATION OPTION IN THE CONTENT PROVIDER DASHBOARD

- Updates to the OpenAIRE's UI Repository Dashboard to support registration and configuration of the endpoints.
- Updates of the usage statistics backend workflow

IMPLEMENTATION TOWARDS A USAGE STATISTICS HUB THAT SUPPORTS THE MUTUAL EXCHANGE OF COUNTER COMPLIANT USAGE STATISTICS REPORTS

- Updates of the usage statistics collection workflow.
- Updates of the usage statistics backend workflow.

6.3 Integration in production

6.3.1 Interaction with other services

The Usage Metrics service interacts with the Information Space by linking usage events to bibliographic metadata items describing research results. This involves not only separate usage statistics for items (e.g., articles or datasets), but also correlated statistics among them, to provide valuable insights of the service.

6.3.2 Timeline

The Usage Metrics service is in currently in production and new functionalities will be released by M24.

7 | INFORMATION SPACE INTERLINKING SERVICES

7.1 Current status

The OpenAIRE Information Space Graph (ISG) includes interlinked objects relative to publications, datasets, software, other products, grants, organizations, data sources, and others. The ISG is produced by a data provision workflow that collects objects harvested (and cleaned) by the aggregation sub-system, enriches them via the information inference sub-system or via end-user claims (additions or corrections), and eventually de-duplicates them via the deduplication sub-system. In order to track this processing pipeline, and to give visibility to the actors in it, OpenAIRE services keep in the objects provenance metadata that specifies which are the sources, algorithms, or users that contributed to their construction.

Today, it is implicit that any data source registered to OpenAIRE to contribute with its content will be visible in OpenAIRE. The benefits for the data source, beyond visibility, are that (i) the data source can bulk collect via OAI-PMH all its records from OpenAIRE, as enriched by the data provision workflow described above; (ii) the data source can focus on specific kinds of enrichments, alerts, or additions and get notifications about them via the Broker Service.

Such a scenario fits with the idea of exchanging content with data sources, but does not satisfy the scenario where a third-party service would like to benefit from (i) and (ii) above *without registering as a data source* in OpenAIRE. For example, consider a service that keeps a catalogue of article metadata collected by users interacting with the same web sources targeted by OpenAIRE. Such a service could be interested to enrich its collection with OpenAIRE metadata, for example interacting with the Broker Service, but this requires the service to become a registered OpenAIRE data source but this would not be possible because a generic catalogue service is not eligible to become an OpenAIRE data source.

7.2 Proposed Enhancements

7.2.1 Objectives

The idea is to include a new category of “invisible scientific article data sources” which can be harvested in the context of OpenAIRE but whose records and provenance are part of the graph but do not appear in the portal and will be referred as “non-public” in the following. The harvested metadata records take part to the deduplication process and can therefore be merged with other records. Consequently, OpenAIRE can generate enrichment, alert, addition events for the data source, as well as a dedicated OAI-PMH set with all of the enriched records. This allows OpenAIRE to serve any requesting data source with **enrichment as-a-service functionalities**.

Note: the idea is to limit to “scientific article sources” as this case is likely to occur, but other classes of invisible sources, relative to different kinds of products (e.g. dataset), may be introduced in the future. The solution below should be replicated for each type of product.

7.2.2 Technical specs

In order deliver this functionality the following tasks must be accomplished:

1. Introduce a new category of non-public OpenAIRE data sources;
2. Introduce a new data collection workflow for this class of data sources, which properly tags the records as non-public and includes in the graph objects that contain the minimal metadata information required to enable deduplication (title, authors, date, DOI) and only one relationship to the data source;
3. Upgrade the deduplication workflows to change their behavior when merging equivalent objects and one of them is tagged as non-public; the merge should not involve the elements of the non-public objects but include its non-public provenance, i.e. the link to the data source;
4. Upgrade the publishing workflow in the publishing sub-system in order to:
 - Make sure an OAI-PMH set for non-public data sources is produced;
 - Make sure that provenance of non-public data sources is not sent to the full-text index, hence visualized in the OpenAIRE portal, Dashboards, and APIs;
 - Make sure the statistics are calculated excluding records tagged as non-public;
 - Make sure provenance of non-public data sources is not propagated into the LOD collection.

7.3 Integration in production

7.3.1 Interaction with other services

As described in the above plan, the action requires changes to several components in different OpenAIRE sub-systems: aggregation, deduplication, and publishing. All services involved in the upgrade are responsibility of CNR.

7.3.2 Timeline (releases)

The plan is to release the upgrade by M24. We expect to progress faster than expected due to the urgency of the task on several fronts.

8 | AMNESIA

8.1 Current status

Amnesia is available as a standalone application or as an online service at <https://amnesia.openaire.eu>. The application is written in JavaScript (frontend) and java (backend). Amnesia offers k -anonymity and k^m -anonymity anonymization algorithms for tabular and set-valued data. It works on tabular and set-valued data that are imported through a friendly wizard, where the user can customize the process by defining the data delimiter, the types of the data fields etc.

Amnesia allows creating and re-using generalization hierarchies. Hierarchies can be created semi-automatically based on the active domain of a data attribute. Amnesia assigns values of the underlying dataset to random groups and then assigns these groups to even broader ones. The user can edit this auto-generated hierarchy or create one from the beginning.

The anonymization algorithms offer global, full domain recoding, e.g., all appearances of a value are replaced in a dataset, together with all sibling nodes in the generalization hierarchy. The most efficient anonymization algorithm is a parallel version of the Flash algorithm for tabular data, and the non-parallel apriori algorithm for set-valued data. Both algorithms work on main memory. The user get a visual representation of the solution space and can easily inspect several statistical properties of each candidate anonymization.

Amnesia works with local text files but it also supports integration with Zenodo.

8.2 Proposed Enhancements

8.2.1 Objectives

The main objectives for Amnesia enhancements is to make the tool more robust and easier to use. In the context of the former we need to alter its anonymization algorithm to handle bigger datasets with lesser memory requirements. Moreover, we will introduce heuristic algorithms, instead of the current exhaustive one, that will reduce the complexity of finding a good solution. To address the latter objective, we will directly target the most tiresome part of the anonymization procedure; the creation of generalization hierarchies. Since many demographic attributes like zipcode, country, marital status etc. are common to many datasets, we will provide predefined hierarchies that will work with most real-world applications.

8.2.2 Technical Specifications

To accomplish the aforementioned objectives the following technical tasks will be fulfilled:

MEMORY CONSCIOUS IMPLEMENTATION

Current version of Amnesia needs to load all data and intermediate structures in main memory. This is a severe limitation on the size of the datasets that can be anonymized, since they have to fit in memory. In OpenAIRE Advance we will create a memory conscious version of the

anonymization algorithms, that will be able to work with a limited memory buffer and use secondary storage for the data that do not fit in memory.

CLUSTER BASED, LOCAL RECODING ALGORITHM

The anonymization algorithms that are supported by Amnesia till now, are based on *global-recording*, i.e., the replacement of all occurrences of a single value in a dataset, e.g., all the occurrences of “Greece” with a more abstract term, e.g., “Europe”. In OpenAIRE advance we will introduce a more flexible anonymization algorithm which will use *local recoding*, i.e., the partial replacement of the occurrences of a specific value in a dataset with a more abstract term. By using partial replacements Amnesia will be able to offer anonymized datasets of improved quality.

PREDEFINED HIERARCHIES

Amnesia offers users the option to create custom generalization hierarchies which are necessary for the anonymization process. It simplifies the procedure by supporting a semi-automatic process based on a given dataset. Still, the process requires significant effort on behalf of the user. At the same time many personal descriptive characteristics are common in a wide range of scientific fields and datasets, e.g., zip code, birthdate, address etc. We plan to create predefined generalization hierarchies for the most common types of descriptive information that is used in datasets with personal information and provide it to users so they can use it with their own data.

8.3 Integration in production

8.3.1 Interaction with other services

In OpenAIRE advance we will extend Amnesia’s interoperability capabilities to make it usable by services like Dataverse²⁰. We will enhance the Amnesia API to be usable through Dataverse and we will also extend Amnesia capabilities to use Dataverse storage.

8.3.2 Timeline (releases)

The roadmap for the releases is the following:

- Interaction with other services on M16
- Predefined hierarchies and Memory conscious implementation on M18
- Cluster based, local recoding algorithm on M22
- The final version will be delivered on M24

²⁰ <https://dataverse.org/>

9 | OPENAIRE OPENDMP

9.1 Current status

The OpenDMP tool has been continuously evolving since January 2018 reaching at the end of the reporting period a mature usable status that is quite adequate for end user feedback collection in real usage scenarios. More specifically, the current version of the platform has gone through a series of releases on a testing infrastructure and can now be utilized by a Data Management Plan responsible to fully describe and track the evolution of a Project's Datasets' descriptions.

More specifically the OpenDMP allows **users** to:

- **Define:**
 - projects/grants where data management plans belong to
 - Data Management Plans and their association with projects, as well as the tracking of their versions
 - Datasets belonging to a DMP
- **Describe** datasets according to templates (Dataset profiles)
- **Associate** researchers / users with DMPs to allow access to their DMP workspace.
- **Execute** of a basic workflow of DMP collaborative authoring (new, draft, validated, published)
- **Validate** of dataset descriptions according to rulesets defined by the administrators

For **administrators**, the system allows the following actions:

- **Define** Dataset profiles
- **Configure** vocabulary sources
- **Manage** all system entities

As a latest addition, the system offers also a public page for DMPs.

Furthermore, the following capabilities are embedded in OpenDMP:

- SSO integration with several Identity Providers, one of those being the EUDAT B2Access service, others being Facebook, Gmail etc.
- Export of printable DMPs
- Export of machine readable DMPs in proprietary XML representation

Among the most powerful **features** of current OpenDMP version are:

- **The Dataset Profile:** A mechanism that allows defining the templates of descriptions of profiles that are made available to system users. The profile is not only carrier of data structure but also of logic for description and validation of a dataset description.
- **The unified interface to external data sources:** A mechanism that assures that the core DMP services is agnostic of the APIs of external data providers and thus can utilize an increasing number of such sources without modifying its code. Currently the role of the bridge to external sources and the role of unifying API provider towards the core DMP is assumed by the EESore

component, while the DMP backend can directly consume external sources that conform to a specific API specification.

- ▣ **The data model of self-sustained yet linked entities** offering where specific entities required to describe datasets may be defined elsewhere yet be sufficiently provided inside the DMP service infrastructure. For instance, projects, researchers, datasets etc. that are defined outside or inside the database of the system.

The following table illustrates the technologies used in OpenDMP.

TABLE 6. OPENDMP TECHNOLOGIES

OpenDMP Technologies	
Front -end	SPA with Angular
Back-end	Spring based JSON REST web services hosted in Apache Tomcat
database management system	PostgreSQL
NoSQL store	Elasticsearch
Platform	Java 8

The system is deployed on a public testing infrastructure at: <https://opendmp.eu/> and is integrated with a number of Identity Providers for SSO and several external sources for provisioning of data for completing dataset descriptions.

Apart from the work performed on the tool, during the reporting period, the development management has been strengthened with the full adoption of GitLab ticketing and code management tools.

9.2 Proposed Enhancements

9.2.1 Objectives

For the future (next period and beyond) several enhancements are planned as described below.

Revamping of User Interface (UI), in order to become easier to use, more attractive to the end user and more compatible with end user devices. This will have multiple beneficial effects to OpenDMP such as:

- Requirement for less support upon adoption, as intuitive UIs directly lead the users to the proper action for performing a task
- More attractive and accessible to onboard more users to the platform

This activity is continuous however immediate priority tasks should do with the intuitiveness of the UI.

Branding of the system, to deliver the proper identity and reference to its end users, along with the tribute to the funders of the project. This activity is both a legal requirement and a sustainability tasks and will be completed before the system begins its official public lifetime.

UI Performance improvements, to improve the user experience in the platform. The complexity of the Dataset profile structure poses significant requirements on client side capabilities and may become an obstacle in processing very complex Data Management Plan templates. Although currently OpenDMP has come a long way of optimisation, further improvement will facilitate adoption and sustainability of the system. This activity is continuous and is combined with backend improvement.

API formalisation, in the sense the interface to external systems needs to be finalized and by published in the form of specifications for external services. This will reduce the need of implementation for new data sources, will lead to less error prone code and will allow the wider incorporation of other services into the system. The activity will span several periods to come, yet in the next one the objective will be to freeze the internal form of the APIs.

Implementation of an interoperable, machine-readable DMP format that will allow DMP tools to exchange and publish actionable DMPs. This activity depends on the progress of external processes (see RDA) and when achieved will allow new features implementation (e.g. DMP content objective validation, simplified analytics etc.). Currently OpenDMP already supports exporting DMPs in machine readable format, however this is not expected to be highly interoperable as it exposes much of the system data model assumptions.

Implementation of Analytics, will provide insights of what is deposited in DMP system and will support system operators, funders and even projects to comprehend their positioning w.r.t. various aspects of data management. However, the task is heavily dependent on the semantics of the attributes of Dataset profile attributes, thus depends partially on the interoperable DMP model, which will define a set of semantics to be applied, as well as a mechanism for assigning semantics to attributes and attribute values inside DMP service that is yet to be designed and will be a task of the upcoming periods.

Authentication extension, with the adoption of more identity providers (IdP) will allow utilizing the system seamlessly in more infrastructures. Several are already supported, and the last implemented is the integration with AAI which is active in development environment and en-route for publication in the current deployment.

Authorization features extension will be required soon to cover more complex scenarios of collaboration over the lifecycle of a DMP and its dataset descriptors. Currently all members of a DMP have equal rights, however this may have to become more fine-grained as for instance members might not have equal access to dataset descriptions or DMP status transitions. This activity will require further feedback from the users to be refined before implementation.

Support for DMP Profiles will allow DMPs (i.e. not only Datasets) to have their own attributes with semantics that will be defined not on a per dataset but on a per DMP basis. The mechanism implementation is en-route; however, the finalization depends on the specification for interoperable actionable DMPs to be published and strategically adopted by the project.

Public pages enhancements will allow visitors to inspect the published content of the DMP system, lookup for datasets of interest and comprehend the Data Management outcome of entities be it funders, projects, organizations etc, which is an additional tool in the direction of data FAIRness. Such instruments will boost the publicity of the project and will contribute to its sustainability. Although public pages do exist and support locating DMPs and dataset descriptors, those may be hugely enhanced. The task depends on the refinement of the branding and visual design of the system and will be completed in the next period.

DMP actionable extensions will allow the DMP tool to interact with other services on the purpose of handling a DMP, in directions such as publishing to repositories, validating data status, validating dataset descriptions, supporting the description of datasets etc. The task depends on the interoperable actionable DMP format definition but also to the collection of further requirements of the community, which will span the next periods of development.

Apart from the planned enhancements, wider testing with new DMP schemes is required to validate the assumptions of generality and stability of the system. This will allow the system to expand to new domains of applicability, such as institutional Data Management Planning.

9.2.2 Technical specs

The various planned enhancements enumerated earlier depend on a number of tasks that will shape their technical specs. Summing up those, the following are the most critical:

- Definition of interoperable, actionable DMP specification as this comes from relevant RDA WGs
- Selection of interoperable services (such as RDA Metadata registries, eInfraCentral) for new integration scenarios and improvement of abstractions provided by service APIs
- Definition of interoperability principles which lay upon common standards (e.g. OAI-PMH, JSON REST web services, XML/JSON etc.) for new integration scenarios.
- Selection of data catalogues for integration with dataset lookup and publishing functionalities.
- Selection of PID model for publication of DMPs and datasets.
- Selection of Data Repositories for integration on dataset depositing and validation.
- Gathering of user feedback for targeting User Interface structure to accommodate the prevailing user needs.

9.3 Integration in production

9.3.1 Interaction with other services

OpenDMP is already integrated with several IdPs and several external sources. More are planned before launching official production period. Among those the most essential is the integration with AAI service, which has been implemented is now to be published on production infrastructure.

9.3.2 Timeline (releases)

The release plan of OpenDMP includes a formal minor release every two months until the end of 2018, a schedule that is maintained, however interim update-releases also take place at shorter periods of time (no less than a week of prior release though).

Currently there are two infrastructures, the development one being refreshed at a twice faster pace than the production one.